

action of these herbicides. Further work to explore this hypothesis is in progress.

Acknowledgement

The financial support of this work from ICAR, New Delhi is gratefully acknowledged. The authors are grateful to Dr. J. B. Singh (G. S. V. M. Medical College, Kanpur) for providing some experimental facilities.

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Potentiometric Determination of Stability Constants of Pr(III), Nd(III), Sm(III), Gd(III) and Dy(III) Complexes with 5-Hydroxy-2-Methyl-1, 4-Naphthaquinone

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Manuscript received 13 October 1980, revised 18 June 1981,
accepted 15 July 1981

A survey of literature^{1,2} shows that no systematic study has been made on the chelating ability of 5-hydroxy-2-methyl-1,4-naphthaquinone, commonly known as plumbagin. We reported³ recently the interaction of Cu(II), Ni(II), Co(II), Mn(II), Zn(II) and Cd(II) with plumbagin in solution. In the present study, the stability constants of the metal chelates of plumbagin with Pr(III), Nd(III), Sm(III), Gd(III) and Dy(III) are determined in 75% v/v ethanol-water mixture at 35° and 0.1 ionic strength.

Experimental

Plumbagin was isolated from the roots of the plant *Plumbago zeylanica*, following the method of Roy *et al.*⁴. The purity of the compound was checked by tlc and melting point. Standard solution of plumbagin was prepared in double distilled ethanol. All other chemicals were of AR grade. The rare earth metal nitrates were obtained from Indian Rare Earths Limited, Udyogamandal. The

metal contents of the solutions were determined by complexometric titrations with EDTA⁵.

An ELICO digital pH meter model LI-120, fitted with a combined electrode type CN-67, capable of reading ± 0.01 was used for pH measurements. The pH values were corrected in aquo-organic mixtures using the method of Van-Uitert and Hass⁶.

The experimental part consists of titration of the following solutions (total volume 50 ml), thermostated at $35^\circ \pm 0.01$ against carbon dioxide free NaOH ($5 \times 10^{-2} M$):

Plumbagin was taken four times in excess of the metal ion to avoid possible hydrolysis of metal ions.

Results and Discussion

The pH titration technique of Irving-Rossotti⁷ was used to obtain the values of \bar{n}_A , \bar{n} and pL from the pH titration curves. The pK_a value of plumbagin obtained from the plot of $\log \left(\frac{\bar{n}_A}{1 - \bar{n}_A} \right)$ vs pH was found to be 9.93 ± 0.02 . The maximum value of \bar{n} obtained in the pH region where hydrolysis of metal ion was negligible, was between 1.5 and 2.0 for Pr(III) and Nd(III) whereas it was between 2 and 3 for Sm(III), Gd(III) and Dy(III). This indicates the formation of 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 complexes in general and also 1 : 3 complexes in case of Sm(III), Gd(III) and Dy(III). The metal-ligand stability constants were computed by means of simultaneous equations as described by Block and McIntyre⁸. The least squares method and the correction term method⁹ were also used to evaluate the formation constants in case of Pr(III) and Nd(III). The refined log K values are stated in Table 1.

TABLE I—STABILITY CONSTANTS OF THE CHELATES OF PR(III), Nd(III), Sm(III), Gd(III) AND Dy(III) WITH PLUMBAGIN IN 75% v/v ETHANOL-WATER MIXTURE AT 35° AND 0.1 IONIC STRENGTH

Metal Ion	log K_1	log K_2	log K_3
Pr(III)	6.65	6.36	—
Nd(III)	6.70	6.51	—
Sm(III)	6.97	6.70	6.49
Gd(III)	7.05	6.72	6.51
Dy(III)	7.31	7.12	6.54

The log K values follow the order Pr(III) < Nd(III) < Sm(III) < Gd(III) < Dy(III). The increase in stabilities of rare earth metal complexes with decrease in ionic or crystal radii indicates the absence of extensive covalent bonding due to non-availability of 4f electrons for bond formation. The near linear plot of Z^2/r vs $\log \beta_2$ of these complexes is in accordance with the Born equation

$\left[\Delta E = \frac{e^2}{2r} \left(1 - \frac{1}{D} \right) \right]$ suggesting that the bond is predominantly ionic. The absence of formation of 1 : 3 complexes in the case of Pr(III) and Nd(III) indicates that these complexes have a greater tendency to undergo hydrolysis probably due to their lower stability.

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (B. V. R.) is grateful to the U. G. C., New Delhi for a teacher fellowship under Faculty Improvement programme.

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Kinetics of Reaction of Bromomethyl Phenyl Sulphoxide with Benzoate Ions

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Manuscript received 29 August 1980, revised 27 April 1981,
accepted 15 July 1981

THE study of bimolecular nucleophilic substitution reactions has received considerable attention during the last two decades¹⁻⁵. The kinetics of the reaction of phenacyl bromide with substituted anilines⁶, benzoate ions⁷ and naphthoate ions⁸ have been reported. Bromomethyl phenyl sulphoxide has been reported to be reactive in nucleophilic substitution reactions⁹ but no systematic kinetic study of the reaction of this compound with benzoate ions has been reported. The results of a detailed kinetic study of the reaction of this bromosulphoxide with a number of benzoate ions in 90% acetone-water (v/v) are reported here.

Experimental

Bromomethyl phenyl sulphoxide was prepared according to literature procedure¹⁰ and purified by vacuum distillation.

Commercial samples of benzoic acids were purified by recrystallization. Solutions of benzoate ions were prepared by dissolving the calculated quantity of the acid in aqueous sodium hydroxide solution and making up to the required volume with AnalaR acetone (E. Merck grade).

Solutions of bromomethyl phenyl sulphoxide and benzoate ion of appropriate concentrations in 90% acetone-water (v/v) were thermostated and mixed together to start the reaction. At suitable regular intervals of time, 10 ml aliquots of the reaction mixture were withdrawn and run into a mixture of nitric and acetic acids. The liberated bromide ion was estimated by titration against standard silver nitrate solution using eosin indicator. When the initial concentrations of the two reactants were equal, the second order rate constants, k (lit. mol⁻¹ sec⁻¹) were calculated using the expression

$$k = \frac{1}{t} \cdot \frac{x}{a(a-x)}$$

where a is the initial [PhSOCH₂Br] and x is [Br⁻] formed in time t (sec). When the initial concentrations were unequal, the values of k were calculated using the expression

$$k = \frac{2.303}{t(a-b)} \log_{10} \frac{b(a-x)}{a(b-x)}$$

where a is the initial concentration of bromosulphoxide, b the initial concentration of benzoate ion and x the concentration of bromide ion formed in time t (sec).

The reaction was studied at three different temperatures and the E_a values were calculated from the slope of the Arrhenius plot of $\log k$ vs $1/T$. Using these E_a values, the values of ΔH^\ddagger , $\log A$ and ΔS^\ddagger were computed.

Results and Discussion

The reaction follows second order rate law, first order each in bromosulphoxide and benzoate ion. This is evident from the constancy of the values of the second order rate constant at different initial concentrations of each of the reactants (Table 1).

TABLE 1—DEPENDENCE OF RATE ON [PhSOCH₂Br] AND [PhCOO⁻] SOLVENT: 90% ACETONE-WATER (v/v); TEMP.: 40°

[PhSOCH ₂ Br] mol. lit ⁻¹	[PhCOO ⁻] mol. lit ⁻¹	10 ⁴ × k (lit. mol ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹)
0.02	0.02	4.00
0.02	0.04	4.09
0.02	0.05	3.81
0.025	0.02	3.72
0.03	0.02	3.80
0.04	0.02	3.84

The second order rate constants and activation parameters for the reaction of bromomethyl phenyl sulphoxide with 13 benzoate ions are recorded in Table 2. The isokinetic relationship $\Delta H^\ddagger = \Delta H_0^\ddagger + \beta \Delta S^\ddagger$ is obeyed in the case of the reactions with